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Superposition principle for the continuity equation in a bounded domain

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Abstract. We consider an initial–boundary value problem for the continuity equation in a class of non-negative measure-valued solutions. We prove that any solution in the considered class can be represented as a superposition of elementary solutions, associated with the solutions of the corresponding ordinary differential equation.

1. Introduction

Let $b: [0, T] \times \mathbb{R}^d \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^d$ be a Borel measurable uniformly bounded time-dependent vector field, where $T > 0$ and $d \in \mathbb{N}$.

Given $x \in \mathbb{R}^d$ let δ_x denote the Dirac measure concentrated at x . With the term *measure* in this work we will, by default, refer to a Borel measure on some underlying space, which will be always clear from the context.

It is well-known that if an absolutely continuous function $\gamma: [0, T] \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^d$ solves

$$\partial_t \gamma(t) = b(t, \gamma(t)) \quad \text{a.e. } t \in (0, T) \quad (\text{ODE})$$

then the family $\{\mu_t\}_{t \in [0, T]}$ of measures on \mathbb{R}^d

$$\mu_t := \delta_{\gamma(t)}, \quad t \in [0, T], \quad (1)$$

solves the continuity equation

$$\partial_t \mu_t + \operatorname{div}_x (b \mu_t) = 0 \quad \text{in } \mathcal{D}'(Q) \quad (\text{CE})$$

where $Q = (0, T) \times \mathbb{R}^d$. Solutions of (CE) having the form (1) will be called *elementary solutions* (associated with solutions γ of (ODE)).

Let

$$\Gamma_b := \{\gamma \in \Gamma : \gamma \text{ is absolutely continuous and solves (ODE)}\}. \quad (2)$$

Note that the set Γ_b is Borel since b is Borel, see [13], Proposition 2.

By linearity of (CE) any linear combination of elementary solutions will solve (CE) as well. More generally, suppose that η is a (possibly signed) Borel measure on

$$\Gamma := C([0, T]; \mathbb{R}^d) \quad (3)$$

such that η is concentrated on the set Γ_b (i.e. satisfies $|\eta|(\Gamma \setminus \Gamma_b) = 0$, where $|\cdot|$ denotes the total variation). Then family $\{\mu_t\}_{t \in [0, T]}$ of measures

$$\mu_t := \int_{\Gamma} \delta_{\gamma(t)} d\eta(\gamma) \quad (4)$$

solves (CE). (Eq. (4) can be understood in the following sense: for any Borel set $E \subset \mathbb{R}^d$ it holds that $\mu_t(E) = \int_{\Gamma} 1_E(\gamma(t)) d\eta(\gamma)$, where 1_E is the indicator of E .)

In other words, any *superposition* of the elementary solutions of (CE) solves (CE) as well. It is therefore natural to ask whether *any* measure-valued solution of (CE) can be represented as a superposition of elementary solutions.

Recall that a family $\{\mu_t\}_{t \in [0, T]}$ of finite measures on \mathbb{R}^d is called a *measure-valued solution* of (CE) if

- (i) $\{\mu_t\}_{t \in [0, T]}$ is a Borel family, i.e. the map $t \mapsto \mu_t(E)$ is Borel measurable for any Borel set $E \subset \mathbb{R}^d$;
- (ii) $\int_0^T |\mu_t|(\mathbb{R}^d) dt < \infty$;
- (iii) Eq. (CE) holds.

Points 1 and 2 here imply that for any bounded Borel function $g: [0, T] \times \mathbb{R}^d$ the function $t \mapsto \int_{\mathbb{R}^d} g(t, x) d\mu_t(x)$ is Borel measurable (see e.g. [1]), therefore the distributional formulation of (CE) is well-defined.

For the class of *non-negative* measure-valued solutions of (CE) the question stated above was positively answered by Ambrosio, Gigli and Savare [11, 2]:

Theorem 1 (Superposition principle). *Let $\{\mu_t\}_{t \in [0, T]}$ be a non-negative measure-valued solution of (CE). Then there exists a non-negative measure η on Γ such that (4) holds for a.e. $t \in [0, T]$.*

Apart from providing a precise characterisation of non-negative measure-valued solutions of (CE), this result can be used together with additional assumptions. For instance, in [5] it was involved in the proof of uniqueness of bounded weak solutions of the continuity equation when $d = 2$ and b is nearly incompressible, autonomous and has bounded variation. This result was recently generalized in [12] for multidimensional non-autonomous nearly incompressible BV vector fields.

In the present work we provide a generalization of Theorem 1 for the case of a bounded domain (instead of the whole space). Solvability of the initial–boundary value problem for the continuity equation with a non-smooth vector field b was studied in [6] (under some weak differentiability assumptions on b).

Let $\Omega \subset \mathbb{R}^d$ be an open set and let $Q := (0, T) \times \Omega$. Suppose that $b: \Omega \times \mathbb{R}^d \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^d$ is a uniformly bounded Borel time-dependent vector field. We will assume that b is extended with 0 to $\mathbb{R}^{d+1} \setminus Q$. Similarly, for any family $\{\mu_t\}_{t \in [0, T]}$ of Borel measures on Ω we will extend the measure μ_t (for each $t \in [0, T]$) with 0 outside of Ω .

Let

$$\Gamma_{\Omega} := \{\gamma \in \Gamma : \gamma^{-1}(\Omega) \neq \emptyset\}$$

denote the set of curves intersecting Ω . Clearly Γ_{Ω} is an open subset of Γ .

In order to take into account the initial and boundary conditions for the continuity equation we will introduce some auxiliary maps. (In Lemma 4 below we prove that these maps are Borel measurable.)

Definition 1. *Given $\gamma \in \Gamma$ let*

$$S_{\gamma} := \inf(\gamma^{-1}(\Omega) \cup \{T\}), \quad E_{\gamma} := \sup(\gamma^{-1}(\Omega) \cup \{0\})$$

If $\gamma \in \Gamma_\Omega$ then S_γ and E_γ are the *times when γ starts and, respectively, ends* in Ω .

Now we are ready to state our main result:

Theorem 2. *Let $\{\mu_t\}_{t \in [0, T]}$ be a Borel family of non-negative measures on \mathbb{R}^d such that $\int_0^T \mu_t(\Omega) dt < \infty$ and $\int_0^T \mu_t(\mathbb{R}^d \setminus \Omega) dt = 0$. Let ν be a signed measure on \mathbb{R}^{d+1} concentrated on ∂Q . Suppose that*

$$\partial_t \mu_t + \operatorname{div}(b\mu_t) = \nu \quad \text{in } \mathcal{D}'(\mathbb{R}^{d+1}) \quad (5)$$

Then there exists a non-negative measure η on Γ such that

(i) for η -a.e. γ we have $S_\gamma < E_\gamma$ and

- $\gamma(t) = \gamma(0)$ for $t \in [0, S_\gamma]$,
- $\gamma(t) \in \Omega$ for a.e. $t \in [S_\gamma, E_\gamma]$,
- $\gamma(t) = \gamma(T)$ for $t \in [E_\gamma, T]$,
- γ solves the ODE $\dot{\gamma}(t) = b(t, \gamma(t))$ a.e. on $[S_\gamma, E_\gamma]$;

(ii) for a.e. $t \in [0, T]$ and any $\varphi \in \mathcal{D}(\mathbb{R}^d)$

$$\int_{\mathbb{R}^d} \varphi(x) d\mu_t(x) = \int_\Gamma \varphi(\gamma(t)) 1_\Omega(\gamma(t)) d\eta(\gamma);$$

(iii) for any $\Phi \in \mathcal{D}(\mathbb{R}^{d+1})$

$$\int_{\mathbb{R}^{d+1}} \Phi(t, x) d\nu(t, x) = \int_\Gamma (\Phi(S_\gamma, \gamma(S_\gamma)) - \Phi(E_\gamma, \gamma(E_\gamma))) d\eta(\gamma), \quad (6a)$$

$$\int_{\mathbb{R}^{d+1}} \Phi(t, x) d|\nu|(t, x) = \int_\Gamma (\Phi(S_\gamma, \gamma(S_\gamma)) + \Phi(E_\gamma, \gamma(E_\gamma))) d\eta(\gamma). \quad (6b)$$

Note that (5) is not a definition of the solution of the initial–boundary value problem for the continuity equation, but a property of such solutions. In particular, this property (i.e. existence of the measure ν) holds for the distributional solutions introduced in [6, Definition 3.4]. The motivation for such setting is the following. Let $U \subset \mathbb{R}^n$ be a bounded open set with a C^1 boundary. Suppose that $V: U \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^n$ is a bounded measurable vector field and $\operatorname{div} V = 0$ (in sense of distributions) inside U . Let us extend V with 0 to $\mathbb{R}^n \setminus U$. Then by [7] there exists a bounded Borel measurable function $g: \partial U \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ such that

$$\operatorname{div}(1_U V) = g \mathcal{H}^{n-1}|_{\partial U} \quad \text{in } \mathcal{D}'(\mathbb{R}^n),$$

where \mathcal{H}^k denotes the k -dimensional Hausdorff measure and $\mu|_E$ denotes the restriction of a measure μ to the set E . From this viewpoint the measure ν in (5) represents both initial and boundary conditions.

2. Currents and their properties

The proof of Theorem 2 is based on the structure of *normal 1-currents*, therefore first we would like to recall some relevant notation.

2.1. Polyvectors and covectors

Let $\Lambda_m(\mathbb{R}^n) \equiv \Lambda_m \mathbb{R}^n$ denote the space of m -vectors (polyvectors) on \mathbb{R}^n . Let $\Lambda^m(\mathbb{R}^n) \equiv \Lambda^m \mathbb{R}^n$ denote the space of m -forms (covectors) on \mathbb{R}^n .

The *inner product* on $\Lambda_m \mathbb{R}^n$ is defined as follows. For simple polyvectors we set

$$(v_1 \wedge \cdots \wedge v_m, w_1 \wedge \cdots \wedge w_m) := \det \|(v_i, w_j)\| \quad (7)$$

Then we extend bilinearly the inner product (\cdot, \cdot) for non-simple polyvectors.

The inner product defined above induces the *euclidean norm* on $\Lambda_m \mathbb{R}^n$:

$$|v| := \sqrt{(v, v)}. \quad (8)$$

2.2. Differential forms and currents

Let $U \subset \mathbb{R}^n$ be an open set. Let $\mathcal{D}^m(U) := \mathcal{D}(U; \Lambda^m \mathbb{R}^n)$ denote the space of smooth m -forms. By definition, an m -dimensional current T is a linear continuous functional on $\mathcal{D}^m(U)$. Let

$$\mathcal{D}_m(U) := \mathcal{D}(U; \Lambda^m \mathbb{R}^n)' \tag{9}$$

denote the space of m -dimensional currents. It is clear that $\Lambda_m(\mathbb{R}^n) \subset \mathcal{D}_m(\mathbb{R}^n)$. More generally, any polyvector field is a current.

The *mass* of $T \in \mathcal{D}_m(\mathbb{R}^n)$ is defined as

$$M(T) := \sup \langle T, \omega \rangle, \tag{10}$$

where the supremum is taken over all differential forms $\omega \in \mathcal{D}^m(\mathbb{R}^n)$ such that

$$|\omega|_\infty := \sup_{x \in \mathbb{R}^d} |\omega(x)| \leq 1. \tag{11}$$

(We use here the euclidean norm of $\Lambda^m(\mathbb{R}^n)$.)

Definition 2. A current S is called a subcurrent of a current T with $M(T) < \infty$ if

$$M(T - S) + M(S) = M(T). \tag{12}$$

If (12) holds then we write $S \subset T$.

2.3. Operations with currents

The *boundary* $\partial T \in \mathcal{D}_{m-1}(\mathbb{R}^n)$ of $T \in \mathcal{D}_m(\mathbb{R}^n)$ is defined by

$$\langle \partial T, \omega \rangle := \langle T, d\omega \rangle, \quad \omega \in \mathcal{D}^{m-1}(\mathbb{R}^n) \tag{13}$$

if $m > 0$. If $m = 0$ then we set $\partial T = 0$.

Let $U \subset \mathbb{R}^n, V \subset \mathbb{R}^k$ be open and let $f: U \rightarrow V \subset \mathbb{R}^k$ be a smooth proper map (i.e. preimage of any compact is compact). The *pushforward* $f_\# T \in \mathcal{D}_m(V)$ of a current $T \in \mathcal{D}_m(U)$, is defined by

$$\langle f_\# T, \omega \rangle := \langle T, f^\# \omega \rangle \quad \omega \in \mathcal{D}^m(\mathbb{R}^n), \tag{14}$$

where $f^\# \omega$ is the pullback of ω with respect to f .

Recall the following definition [8, Definition 3.7]:

Definition 3. Let $T \in \mathcal{D}_m(\mathbb{R}^n)$. A current $C \in \mathcal{D}_m(\mathbb{R}^n)$ is called a cycle of T if $C \subset T$ and $\partial C = 0$. The current T is called acyclic if $C = 0$ is the only cycle of T .

2.4. Examples of currents

The simplest example of a current is an oriented segment. Let $[a, b] \subset \mathbb{R}$. We define

$$\langle [[a, b]], \omega \rangle := \int_a^b \omega \tag{15}$$

for any $\omega \in \mathcal{D}^1(\mathbb{R})$ (smooth compactly supported 1-form). Clearly $[[a, b]] \in \mathcal{D}_1(\mathbb{R})$.

More generally, suppose that $v \in L^1(\mathbb{R}^n; \mathbb{R}^n)$. Given $\omega \in \mathcal{D}^1(\mathbb{R}^n)$ define

$$\langle P, \omega \rangle := \int_{\mathbb{R}^n} \langle \omega(x), v(x) \rangle dx.$$

Then P is a 1-current on \mathbb{R}^n .

If $\theta: [a, b] \mapsto \mathbb{R}^n$ is Lipschitz and $\theta' \neq 0$ a.e., then we define

$$[[\theta]] := \theta_{\#}[[a, b]] \quad (16)$$

Clearly $[[\theta]] \in \mathcal{D}_1(\mathbb{R}^n)$. Let us show that if, in addition, θ is a simple curve with fixed orientation (or even if it intersects itself in finitely many points) then $[[\theta]]$ does not depend on the choice of the parametrization θ .

Let \mathcal{L}^n denote the Lebesgue measure and let \mathcal{H}^k denote the k -dimensional Hausdorff measure on \mathbb{R}^n .

From the definition of the pullback of a differential form (see e.g. [3], def. 6.2.7) it follows that

$$(\theta^{\#}\omega)(t) = \langle \omega(\theta(t)), \theta'(t) \rangle dt \quad (17)$$

Then using Area formula we get

$$\begin{aligned} \langle [[\theta]], \omega \rangle &= \langle [[a, b], \theta^{\#}\omega \rangle \\ &= \int_a^b \langle \omega(\theta(t)), \theta'(t) \rangle dt \\ &= \int_a^b \langle \omega(x), \tau(x) \rangle d\mathcal{H}^1(x), \end{aligned} \quad (18)$$

where $\tau(\theta(t)) = \theta'(t)/|\theta'(t)|$ for a.e. $t \in [a, b]$. In other words, we have proved that

$$[[\theta]] = \tau \mathcal{H}^1 \llcorner \theta([a, b]), \quad (19)$$

where $\mu \llcorner A$ denotes the restriction of the measure μ on the set A . Hence $[[\theta]]$ does not depend on the choice of the parametrization θ (which preserves the orientation).

2.5. Polar decomposition of a current with finite mass

Given a topological space \mathfrak{X} let $\mathcal{M}(\mathfrak{X})$ denote the set of finite Borel measures on \mathfrak{X} . Let $\mathcal{M}_+(\mathfrak{X}) \subset \mathcal{M}(\mathfrak{X})$ denote the set of non-negative measures.

Let $\mu \in \mathcal{M}_+(\mathbb{R}^n)$. Let $f: \mathbb{R}^n \rightarrow \Lambda_m(\mathbb{R}^n)$ be a Borel polyvector field on \mathbb{R}^n such that $f \in L^1(\mu)$. Then one can define an m -current $T := f\mu$ as follows:

$$\langle T, \omega \rangle = \int_{\mathbb{R}^n} \langle \omega, f \rangle d\mu, \quad \forall \omega \in \mathcal{D}^m(\mathbb{R}^n). \quad (20)$$

Lemma 1. *If $f \in L^1(\mathbb{R}^n, \mu; \Lambda_m \mathbb{R}^n)$ then*

$$M(f\mu) = \int_{\mathbb{R}^n} |f| d\mu. \quad (21)$$

Proof. First, notice that $T: \omega \mapsto \langle f\mu, \omega \rangle$ can be extended by continuity for any $\omega \in C_b(\mathbb{R}^n; \Lambda^m \mathbb{R}^n)$. Using Lusin's theorem we extend T further to any bounded Borel $\omega: \mathbb{R}^n \rightarrow \Lambda^m \mathbb{R}^n$. Then in the definition of mass (10) we can take sup over all bounded Borel differential forms.

By (10) $M(f\mu) \leq \int_{\mathbb{R}^n} |f| d\mu$.

Let us define a Borel differential form $\omega: \mathbb{R}^n \rightarrow \Lambda^m \mathbb{R}^n$ by

$$\langle \omega, v \rangle := \frac{(f, v)}{|f|}. \quad (22)$$

(Without loss of generality we may assume that $f \neq 0$.) Clearly $|\omega| = 1$, and

$$\langle f\mu, \omega \rangle = \int_{\mathbb{R}^n} \langle \omega, f \rangle d\mu = \int_{\mathbb{R}^n} |f| d\mu. \quad (23)$$

□

All currents with finite mass have the form (20) (see e.g. [3, §7.2]):

Proposition 1 (Polar decomposition). *Let $T \in \mathcal{D}_m(\mathbb{R}^n)$ and suppose that $M(T) < \infty$. Then there exists a Borel polyvector field $f: \mathbb{R}^n \rightarrow \Lambda_m(\mathbb{R}^n)$ such that $\|f(x)\| = 1$ for all $x \in \mathbb{R}^n$ and a finite non-negative Borel measure μ on \mathbb{R}^n such that (20) holds.*

(Proposition 1 essentially follows from the Riesz representation theorem.)

It is easy to see that this decomposition is unique in the following sense: if $T = g\nu$ for some other non-negative Borel measure ν on \mathbb{R}^n and Borel polyvector field $g: \mathbb{R}^n \rightarrow \Lambda_m(\mathbb{R}^n)$ such that $\|g(x)\| = 1 \forall x \in \mathbb{R}^n$ then $\nu = \mu$ (as measures) and the equality $f = g$ holds μ -a.e. We will therefore denote

$$|T| := \mu \quad (24)$$

where μ is the measure provided by Proposition 1.

Clearly for the current $[\theta]$ defined in (16) one has

$$|[\theta]| = \mathcal{H}^1 \llcorner \theta([a, b]) \quad \text{and} \quad |\partial[\theta]| = \begin{cases} \delta_{\theta(0)} + \delta_{\theta(1)}, & \theta(0) \neq \theta(1); \\ 0, & \theta(0) = \theta(1). \end{cases} \quad (25)$$

Lemma 2. *Suppose that $\mu = \mu_1 + \mu_2$ and $\mu_1 \perp \mu_2$ are non-negative finite Borel measures. Let $f \in L^1(\mathbb{R}^n, \mu; \Lambda^m \mathbb{R}^n)$. Then*

$$M(\mu f) = M(\mu_1 f) + M(\mu_2 f). \quad (26)$$

Proof. The proof follows immediately from (21). □

The generic form of subcurrent of a current with finite mass can be described as follows:

Proposition 2. *Let $\mu \in \mathcal{M}_+(\mathbb{R}^n)$ and $f \in L^1(\mathbb{R}^n, \mu; \Lambda^m \mathbb{R}^n)$. Then $S \in \mathcal{D}_m(\mathbb{R}^n)$ is a subcurrent of $T := f\mu$ if and only if*

$$S = g\mu \quad (27)$$

where $g \in L^1(\mathbb{R}^n, \mu; \Lambda^m \mathbb{R}^n)$ satisfies

$$g(x) \in \text{conv}\{0, f(x)\} := \{tf(x) \mid t \in [0, 1]\} \quad (28)$$

for μ -a.e. $x \in \mathbb{R}^n$.

Proof. By Proposition 1 there exists $\nu \in \mathcal{M}_+(\mathbb{R}^n)$ and $g \in L^1(\mathbb{R}^n, \mu; \Lambda^m \mathbb{R}^n)$ such that $S = g\nu$. By Radon-Nikodym theorem there exist mutually singular $\nu^a, \nu^s \in \mathcal{M}_+(\mathbb{R}^n)$ such that $\nu = \nu^a + \nu^s$, $\nu^a \ll \mu$ and $\nu^s \perp \mu$. Then

$$\begin{aligned} M(f\mu) &\stackrel{(12)}{=} M(f\mu - g\nu) + M(g\nu) \\ &\stackrel{(26)}{=} M(f\mu - g\nu^a - g\nu^s) + M(g\nu^a) + M(g\nu^s) \\ &\stackrel{(26)}{=} M(f\mu - g\nu^a) + M(g\nu^a) + 2M(g\nu^s). \end{aligned}$$

On the other hand by triangle inequality

$$M(f\mu) \leq M(f\mu - g\nu^a) + M(g\nu^a)$$

hence $2M(g\nu^s) = 0$, i.e. $\nu^s = 0$.

Therefore without loss of generality we can assume that $S = g\mu$.

Again using (12) we get

$$\int_{\mathbb{R}^n} (|f - g| + |g|) d\mu = \int_{\mathbb{R}^n} |f| d\mu. \quad (29)$$

Let $E \subset \mathbb{R}^n$ be a Borel set. By triangle inequality $|f(x)| \leq |f(x) - g(x)| + |g(x)|$ for any $x \in \mathbb{R}^n$ hence

$$\int_{\mathbb{R}^n \setminus E} (|f - g| + |g|) d\mu \geq \int_{\mathbb{R}^n \setminus E} |f| d\mu. \quad (30)$$

Subtracting (30) from (29) we get

$$\int_E (|f - g| + |g|) d\mu \leq \int_E |f| d\mu. \quad (31)$$

Again by triangle inequality the opposite inequality holds, hence in fact (31) is an equality. By arbitrariness of E we conclude that

$$|f(x) - g(x)| + |g(x)| = |f(x)| \quad (32)$$

for μ -a.e. $x \in \mathbb{R}^n$. Let $f_1 := \frac{(g,f)}{|f|^2} f$, $f_2 := \frac{(f-g,f)}{|f|^2} f = f - f_1$. Let $h := g - f_1$. Then $f - g - f_2 = -h$. Since the norm is euclidean,

$$|f - g| + |g| = |f_1| + |f_2| + 2|h|.$$

By triangle inequality $|f| \leq |f_1| + |f_2|$ hence using (32) and the equality above we get $h = 0$. Consequently $|f_1| \leq |f|$. □

Corollary 1. *Suppose that $\mu \in \mathcal{M}_+(\mathbb{R}^n)$, $f \in L^1(\mathbb{R}^n, \mu; \Lambda_1 \mathbb{R}^n)$ has the components (f_1, \dots, f_n) . If $f_1 > 0$ μ -a.e. then the current $P := f\mu$ is acyclic.*

Proof. Let $C \subset P$ be a cycle of P . By Proposition 2 $C = g\mu$ with some g such that $g_1 \geq 0$. For every $k \in \mathbb{N}$ set $\omega^k(x) := x_1 \vee k \wedge (-k)$. Then ω^k is continuous and bounded, so we can test and deduce that

$$0 = \langle \partial C, \omega^k \rangle = \langle C, d\omega^k \rangle = \int_{\{x_1 \in [-k, +k]\}} g_1(x) d\mu(x) = \int_{\mathbb{R}^n} 1_{\{x_1 \in [-k, +k]\}}(x) g_1(x) d\mu(x) \rightarrow \int_{\mathbb{R}^n} g_1 d\mu(x)$$

where the passage to the limit is allowed by dominated convergence ($g_1 \in L^1(\mu)$). □

2.6. *Decomposition of normal 1-currents*

Our main tool is the decomposition result for normal 1-currents obtained originally in [9] for finite-dimensional Euclidean spaces, and generalized in [8] for arbitrary complete separable metric spaces. Given metric spaces M, N let $\text{Lip}(M, N)$ denote the metric space of bounded Lipschitz continuous maps from M to N , endowed with the standard sup norm. We state the decomposition result for \mathbb{R}^n following [8]:

Theorem 3 (Smirnov; Paolini, Stepanov). *Let P be an acyclic normal 1-current on \mathbb{R}^n . Then there exists a finite measure $\xi \geq 0$ on $X := \text{Lip}([0, 1]; \mathbb{R}^n)$ such that*

- (i) ξ -a.e. θ is simple;
- (ii) for any $\omega \in \mathcal{D}^1(\mathbb{R}^n)$

$$\langle P, \omega \rangle = \int_X \langle \llbracket \theta \rrbracket, \omega \rangle d\xi(\theta),$$

where $\llbracket \cdot \rrbracket$ was introduced in (16);

- (iii) for any $\varphi \in \mathcal{D}^1(\mathbb{R}^n)$

$$\int_{\mathbb{R}^n} \varphi d|P| = \int_X \left(\int_{\mathbb{R}^n} \varphi(x) d|\llbracket \theta \rrbracket|(x) \right) d\xi(\theta),$$

where $|\llbracket \theta \rrbracket|$ is the total variation of the current $\llbracket \theta \rrbracket$, see (24) and (25);

- (iv) for any $\varphi \in \mathcal{D}^1(\mathbb{R}^n)$

$$\langle |\partial P|, \omega \rangle = \int_X \langle |\partial \llbracket \theta \rrbracket|, \omega \rangle d\xi(\theta).$$

We will refer to any measure ξ given by Theorem 3 as to a *decomposition of P* .

Similarly to the proof of Lemma 1 one can observe that the equalities (1)–(3) of Theorem 3 hold not only for the smooth test functions and forms φ and ω , but also for merely bounded and Borel ones.

Let $\varphi \in \mathcal{D}(\mathbb{R}^n)$ and $\omega := d\varphi$. By Theorem 3(2)

$$\langle \partial P, \varphi \rangle = \int_X \langle \partial \llbracket \theta \rrbracket, \varphi \rangle d\xi(\theta). \tag{33}$$

The following result was obtained in [10]:

Proposition 3. *Let $\mu \in \mathcal{M}_+(\mathbb{R}^n)$. Suppose that $B: \mathbb{R}^n \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^n$ is Borel measurable, $B \neq 0$ on \mathbb{R}^n and $B \in L^1(\mathbb{R}^n, \mu)$. Suppose that 1-current $P := B\mu$ is normal. Then for any decomposition $\xi \in \mathcal{M}(X)$ of P (provided by Theorem 3) for ξ -a.e. $\theta \in X$ it holds that*

$$\dot{\theta}(s) = |\dot{\theta}(s)| \frac{B(\theta(s))}{|B(\theta(s))|} \quad \text{for a.e. } s \in [0, 1]. \tag{34}$$

For convenience of the reader let us present the proof of this result.

Proof. We apply Theorem 3 (2) with $\omega := |B|^{-1} B_i dx^i$:

$$\int_{\mathbb{R}^n} 1 d\mu = \int_X \int_0^1 \theta'(s) \cdot \frac{B}{|B|}(\theta(s)) ds d\xi(\theta).$$

Since $|P| = \mu$, from Theorem 3 (3) with $\varphi \equiv 1$ it follows that

$$\int_{\mathbb{R}^n} 1 d\mu = \int_X \int_0^1 |\theta'(s)| ds d\xi(\theta).$$

The equalities above imply that

$$\int_X \int_0^1 (|\theta'(s)| - \theta'(s) \cdot \frac{B}{|B|}(\theta(s))) ds d\xi(\theta) = 0.$$

By Cauchy–Bunyakovsky inequality the integrand is non-negative. Hence for ξ -a.e. $\theta \in X$

$$|\theta'(s)| - \theta'(s) \cdot \frac{B}{|B|}(\theta(s)) = 0$$

holds for a.e. $s \in [0, 1]$. Clearly this equality is only possible when $\theta'(s) = |\theta'(s)| \frac{B}{|B|}(\theta(s))$. \square

Corollary 2. *In addition to the assumptions of Proposition 3 suppose that $B_1 \equiv 1$ on \mathbb{R}^n and there exists $C > 0$ such that $|B_j| \leq C$ for any $j \in 2, 3, \dots, n$. Then for any $\tau, \tau' \in [0, 1]$ and any $j \in 2, 3, \dots, n$*

$$|\theta_1(\tau') - \theta_1(\tau)| \geq \frac{1}{C} |\theta_j(\tau') - \theta_j(\tau)| \quad (35)$$

Proof. Since $B_1 = 1$ and $|B_j| \leq C$ the following inequalities hold:

$$\begin{cases} B_1(z) + \frac{1}{C} B_j(z) & \geq 0, \\ B_1(z) - \frac{1}{C} B_j(z) & \geq 0. \end{cases}$$

Substituting $z = \theta(s)$ and multiplying these inequalities by $|\dot{\theta}(s)| \frac{1}{|B(\theta(s))|}$ in view of (34) we get

$$\begin{cases} \dot{\theta}_1(s) + \frac{1}{C} \dot{\theta}_j(s) & \geq 0, \\ \dot{\theta}_1(s) - \frac{1}{C} \dot{\theta}_j(s) & \geq 0. \end{cases}$$

Integrating with respect to s from τ to τ' (observe that $B_1 \geq 0$) we get the desired result. \square

3. Continuity equation and 1-currents

In this section, similar to section 2.6, we denote $X := \text{Lip}([0, 1]; \mathbb{R}^n)$, where $n = d + 1$ is the dimension of the spacetime.

Before proving Theorem 2 it remains to state several technical propositions.

Let

$$X_Q := \{\theta \in X : \theta^{-1}(Q) \neq \emptyset\}.$$

Clearly X_Q is an open subset of X .

Given $c > 0$ let X_c denote the closed subspace of X consisting of $\theta: [0, 1] \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^{d+1}$ with the components $(\theta_1, \dots, \theta_{d+1})$ such that

- $s \mapsto \theta_1(s)$ is non-decreasing;
- for any $\tau, s \in [0, 1]$ and any $j \in 2, \dots, d + 1$

$$|\theta_j(\tau) - \theta_j(s)| \leq c |\theta_1(\tau) - \theta_1(s)|. \quad (36)$$

One can say that the elements of X_c are *timelike* curves in the spacetime, which are confined by a family of cones with a fixed shape.

Consider $\theta \in X_c$ with the components $(\theta_1, \dots, \theta_{d+1})$. By definition of X_c for any $t \in \theta_1([0, 1])$ the equation

$$\theta_1(s) = t$$

has at least one solution, i.e. $\theta_1^{-1}(t) \neq \emptyset$. Let

$$s_\theta(t) := \begin{cases} 0, & t < \theta_1(0); \\ \min \theta_1^{-1}(t), & t \in \theta_1([0, 1]); \\ 1, & t > \theta_1(1). \end{cases}$$

Let us define the function $\gamma_\theta: [0, T] \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^d$ as the composition

$$\gamma_\theta := (\theta_2, \dots, \theta_{d+1}) \circ s_\theta.$$

In general θ_1 may be not injective and therefore s_θ might be discontinuous. Nevertheless γ_θ is Lipschitz continuous by (36).

Lemma 3. *The map*

$$g: X_c \ni \theta \mapsto \gamma_\theta \in \Gamma$$

is continuous.

Proof. Consider $\theta, \vartheta \in X_c$ and suppose that $\varepsilon := \|\gamma_\vartheta - \gamma_\theta\| > 0$. Let $t \in [0, T]$ be such that $|\gamma_\vartheta(t) - \gamma_\theta(t)| = \varepsilon$. Let $z := s_\theta(t)$. By (36) the image $\theta([0, 1])$ is contained in the cone

$$K_t := \{(\tau, \xi) \in \mathbb{R} \times \mathbb{R}^d : \|\xi - \gamma_\theta(t)\| \leq c|\tau - t|\}.$$

Hence

$$\|\vartheta - \theta\| \geq \text{dist}(\vartheta(z), \theta(z)) \geq \text{dist}(\vartheta(z), K_t) \geq \varepsilon \sin \varphi,$$

where $\varphi = \arctan \frac{1}{c}$. Therefore g is Lipschitz continuous with the Lipschitz constant $\frac{1}{\sin \varphi}$. \square

Lemma 4. *The maps $\Gamma_\Omega \ni \gamma \mapsto S_\gamma \in \mathbb{R}$ and $\Gamma_\Omega \ni \gamma \mapsto E_\gamma \in \mathbb{R}$ are Borel measurable.*

Proof. Let $\bar{\gamma} \in \Gamma_\Omega$. For any $\varepsilon > 0$ there exists $t \in [S_{\bar{\gamma}}, S_{\bar{\gamma}} + \varepsilon)$ such that $\gamma(t) \in \Omega$. Since Ω is open we can always find $\delta > 0$ such that $B_\delta(\bar{\gamma}(t)) \subset \Omega$. Hence for any $\gamma \in B_\delta(\bar{\gamma})$ it holds that

$$S_\gamma \leq t < S_{\bar{\gamma}} + \varepsilon$$

Therefore $\gamma \mapsto S_\gamma$ is upper semicontinuous. By an analogous argument the map $\gamma \mapsto E_\gamma$ is lower semicontinuous. Consequently, both maps are Borel measurable. \square

Now we are ready to prove our main result:

of Theorem 2. Let $B: \mathbb{R}^{d+1} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^{d+1}$ be the vector field with components

$$B(z) := (1, b_1(z), b_2(z), \dots, b_d(z)), \quad z \in \mathbb{R}^{d+1}.$$

Let us introduce the measure μ on \mathbb{R}^{d+1} as follows:

$$\mu(E) = \int_0^T \int_{\mathbb{R}^d} 1_E(t, x) d\mu_t(x) dt \quad (37)$$

for any Borel set $E \subset \mathbb{R}^{d+1}$, where $1_E(z) = 1_E(z_1, z_2, \dots, z_{d+1})$ is the indicator function for the set E . Notice that μ is a Borel measure, because the family $\{\mu_t\}_{t \in [0, T]}$ is Borel (see e.g. [1]).

It is easy to check that by (5)

$$\operatorname{div}(B\mu) = \nu \quad \text{in } \mathcal{D}'(\mathbb{R}^{d+1}), \quad (38)$$

where the divergence is taken with respect to the space-time $(t, x) = (t, x_1, \dots, x_d)$. (Recall that both μ_t and b are extended with 0 outside of Q .)

Therefore by Corollary 1 the current $P := B\mu$ is acyclic. Hence by Theorem 3 there exists a decomposition ξ of the current P .

By Proposition 3 the measure ξ is concentrated on the solutions of (34). In view of Corollary 2 there exists a constant $C > 0$ such that ξ is concentrated on X_C (which was introduced above in Section 3). Therefore for ξ -a.e. θ we can define $\gamma_\theta := g(\theta)$, where g is the map introduced in Lemma 3.

The measure μ by definition is concentrated on Q . Hence by the equality (3) of Theorem 3 for ξ -a.e. θ it holds that $|\llbracket \theta \rrbracket|(\mathbb{R}^{d+1} \setminus Q) = 0$. For any such θ let $S := \{s \in [0, 1] : \theta(s) \notin Q\}$ and $\gamma := g(\theta)$. Then $\mathcal{H}^1(\theta(S)) = 0$. It is obvious that $\{t \in \theta_1([0, 1]) : \gamma(t) \notin \Omega\} \subset \pi(\theta(S))$, where $\pi: [0, T] \times \mathbb{R}^d \ni (t, x) \mapsto t$ is the standard projection. Consequently $\mathcal{L}^1(t \in \theta_1([0, 1]) : \gamma(t) \notin \Omega) \leq \mathcal{H}^1(\pi(\theta(S))) \leq \mathcal{H}^1(\theta(S)) = 0$ (see e.g. (1.4.6) in [4]). Therefore for a.e. $t \in \theta_1([0, 1])$ it holds that $\gamma(t) \in \Omega$. Hence $S_\gamma = \theta_1(0)$ and $E_\gamma = \theta_1(1)$. Since ξ -a.e. θ is injective and belongs to X_C , we also have $S_\gamma < E_\gamma$.

By Area formula and (34) for any $t \in [S_\gamma, E_\gamma]$ we have

$$\begin{aligned} \int_{S_\gamma}^t b_j(\tau, \gamma(\tau)) d\tau &= \int_{\theta_1(0)}^{\theta_1(t)} b_j(\theta_1(s), \gamma(\theta_1(s))) \theta_1'(s) ds \\ &= \int_{\theta_1(0)}^{\theta_1(t)} b_j(\theta_1(s), \gamma(\theta_1(s))) \frac{|\theta'(s)|}{|B(\theta(s))|} ds = \int_{\theta_1(0)}^{\theta_1(t)} b_j(\theta(s)) \frac{|\theta'(s)|}{|B(\theta(s))|} ds \\ &= \int_{\theta_1(0)}^{\theta_1(t)} \theta_j'(s) ds = \theta_j(\theta_1(t)) - \theta_j(\theta_1(S_\gamma)) = \gamma_j(t) - \gamma_j(S_\gamma), \end{aligned}$$

where $j = 1, 2, \dots, d$. Hence γ satisfies the ODE $\gamma'(t) = b(t, \gamma(t))$ for a.e. $t \in [S_\gamma, E_\gamma]$.

Let $\Phi = (1_Q \varphi, 0, \dots, 0)$, where $\varphi: \mathbb{R}^{d+1} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ is a bounded Borel function. Then

$$\begin{aligned} \int_0^T \int_{\mathbb{R}^d} \varphi d\mu_t dt &= \int_Q B \cdot \Phi d\mu = \langle P, \Phi \rangle = \int_{X_C} \langle \llbracket \theta \rrbracket, \Phi \rangle d\xi(\theta) \\ &= \int_{X_C} \int_0^1 \Phi(\theta(s)) \cdot \theta'(s) ds d\xi(\theta) \\ &= \int_{X_C} \int_0^1 (1_Q \cdot \varphi)(\theta(s)) \theta_1'(s) ds d\xi(\theta) \\ &= \int_{X_C} \int_0^1 (1_Q \cdot \varphi)(\theta_1(s), \gamma_\theta(\theta_1(s))) \theta_1'(s) ds d\xi(\theta) \\ &= \int_{X_C} \int_0^T (1_Q \cdot \varphi)(t, \gamma_\theta(t)) dt d\xi(\theta) && \text{(by Area formula)} \\ &= \int_0^T \int_{X_C} (1_Q \cdot \varphi)(t, \gamma_\theta(t)) d\xi(\theta) dt && \text{(by Fubini's theorem)} \\ &= \int_0^T \int_\Gamma (1_Q \cdot \varphi)(t, \gamma(t)) d\eta(\gamma) dt, \end{aligned}$$

where $\eta := g_{\#}\xi$ is the pushforward of the measure ξ under the map g . The measure η is well-defined by Lemma 3. Hence the claim (3) of Theorem 2 is proved.

It remains to prove claim (4) of Theorem 2. Arguing as above and using (33) we obtain (6a). By Theorem 3(4)

$$\begin{aligned} \int_{\mathbb{R}^{d+1}} \varphi d\nu &= \langle |\partial P|, \varphi \rangle \\ &= \int_{X_C} [\varphi(\theta(0)) + \varphi(\theta(1))] d\xi(\theta) \\ &= \int_{X_C} [\varphi(\theta_1(0), \gamma_\theta(\theta_1(0))) + \varphi(\theta_1(1), \gamma_\theta(\theta_1(1)))] d\xi(\theta) \\ &= \int_{X_C} [\varphi(S_{\gamma_\theta}, \gamma_\theta(S_{\gamma_\theta})) + \varphi(E_{\gamma_\theta}, \gamma_\theta(E_{\gamma_\theta}))] d\xi(\theta) \\ &= \int_{\Gamma} [\varphi(S_\gamma, \gamma(S_\gamma)) + \varphi(E_\gamma, \gamma(E_\gamma))] d\eta(\gamma) \end{aligned}$$

Hence (6b) is proved. □

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